

Morphometric Study of Upper End of Tibia and its Clinical Importance in West Bengal Population**Madhushree Pal¹, Nabanita Chakraborty², Ankur Bhattacharjee³, Dona Saha⁴**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Anatomy, Barasat Government Medical College, North 24 Parganas, West Bengal, 700124²Associate Professor, Department of Anatomy, Jagannath Gupta Institute of Medical Sciences & Hospital, Kolkata, West Bengal 700137³Assistant Professor, Department of Anatomy, Jagannath Gupta Institute of Medical Sciences & Hospital, Kolkata, West Bengal 700137.⁴Associate Professor, Barasat Government Medical College, North 24 Parganas, West Bengal

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract**Introduction:** The knee joint is a compound synovial joint. Upper end of tibia is an important component of knee joint. Hence the knowledge regarding the morphometry of the articular surface of the tibial condyles as well as intercondylar area is utmost necessary to formulate a baseline data for future studies and to compare the current data with previous literature.**Aims and Objectives:** This study measures the upper end of the tibia in the West Bengal population to provide accurate anatomical data. It also compares these measurements with existing knee prostheses used in total knee replacement to assess their suitability and guide better prosthesis design.**Materials and Methods:** The study has been carried out on 50 dry adult tibia of unknown sex in the department of Anatomy in a tertiary care hospital of West Bengal. Measurements were taken by using the digital Vernier's caliper and statistical analysis has been done.**Results:** It was observed that the mean Antero-posterior and Transverse diameter of Medial Tibial Condyle (MTC) are more than Antero-posterior and Transverse diameter of Lateral Tibial Condyle (LTC). The mean of transverse diameter of total condylar area is greater than that of Antero-posterior diameter of total condylar area.**Conclusion:** The present study is to deliver a baseline data consisting of morphometric details of upper end of tibia which will help for knee arthroplasty procedure.**Keywords:** Knee prosthesis, Tibial Condyles, Intercondylar area.

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Introduction

Femoro-tibial articulation of knee joint is responsible for body weight transmission of human beings. Osteoarthritis is the main cause of total knee replacement. So, due to better outcome of orthopedic operation, detailed data of morphometric parameters of lower end of femur and upper end of tibia is needed. Reeti R et al found in her study that antero-posterior diameter was more than the transverse diameters of tibial condyles.[1]

Ahmed N et al done correlation between antero-posterior diameter of intercondylar area of right and left tibia in his study.[2] Frelat MA found the prenatal origin of population differences in the crural index indicates a genetic determination of these differences whereas limb length and relative

epiphyseal width likely are both genetically and environmentally determined.[3]

Materials and Methods**Methodology:** After approval from institutional ethical committee, the study was initiated. Following morphometric parameters was noted using digital vernier caliper on 50 adult human dry tibia: Transverse and anteroposterior diameters of the condyles, Transverse and anteroposterior diameters of the intercondylar area of upper end of tibia.**Study Design:** Descriptive cross-sectional morphometric study.**Place of study:** Barasat Government Medical College.**Period of study:** 1 Year.

Figure 1:

Result

Table 1: AP and TR of MTC, LTC and TCA of Tibial upper end (n=50)

	MTC		LTC		Total Condylar Area	
	AP	TR	AP	TR	AP	TR
Mean	41.9	28.5	36.6	29.3	42.7	66.1
Standard Dev	3.9069	2.2278	4.8608	3.8525	3.997	5.357
Standard error	1.1103	0.6331	1.3814	1.0949	1.1359	1.5224

Table 2: Comparative Analysis of Mean Condylar Measurements (in mm) Across Different Studies

	MTC		LTC		Total Condylar Area	
	AP	TR	AP	TR	AP	TR
Mean						
Our Study	41.9	28.5	36.6	29.3	42.7	66.1
Ahmad N et al	40.19	28.38	36.41	27.9	42.52	66.33
Gupta C et al	44.5	27.3	40.7	27.9	45.7	68.3
Mukhia R et al	46.38	28.79	39.14	27.86	-	-
Murlimanju BV et al	39.8	26.7	33.6	26.1	-	-
Babacan S et al	42.61	32.07	37.14	31.69	45.98	

Figure 2:

Figure 3:

Analysis revealed that anterior-posterior diameters (APDs) of medial and lateral condyle were 41.91 ± 3.91 and 36.57 ± 4.86 (mean \pm sd) with ranges of 13.5 and 14.5 mm, respectively.

Respective transverse diameters (TD) were estimated to be 28.47 ± 2.23 and 29.28 ± 3.85 (mean \pm sd) along with their ranges of 8.5 and 14.2 mm, respectively. APD and TD of total condylar area (TCA) were estimated as 42.73 ± 3.99 and 66.09 ± 5.36 (mean \pm sd) with ranges of 12.8 and 18.7 mm, respectively. APDs were found significantly larger than TDs in both condyles (Independent 't' = 21.131 & 8.307 with P values of 0.000 in both cases at df=98). However, in TCA, the TD was found to be significantly larger than APD (Independent 't' = 24.722 with P values of 0.000 at df=98).

Discussion

Reeti R et al [1] conducted their study on 50 adult tibia (25 of right side and 25 of left side) and found that the measurements were more on the right side, but the difference was statistically insignificant. It was found that antero-posterior diameter was more than transverse diameter in case of medial condyle on both the sides. Antero-posterior diameter of the intercondylar area was more on the left side, but the difference was statistically insignificant. Ahmad N et al [2] performed his study on 60 adult tibia of both sides (right 34, left 26) and found that the mean AP diameter of the medial condyle was more for right side than left while the transverse diameter was more for left side than right. In his study, Frelat MA et al [3] found that Africans and Europeans have a very similar average length and average shape of multivariate analysis of upper end of tibia until about 10 years of age. During adolescence Africans have a higher growth rate

leading to longer adult bones with narrower epiphysis relative to the diaphysis. As per Bhadoria P et al [4], mean AP and transverse diameters of MTC are more than LTC. In our study we also found greater AP and transverse diameters in case of MTC than LTC.

Chaitra D et al [5] reported that the conventional prosthesis available in the market are designed for the Caucasians. When compared to the Caucasians, south Indian population have smaller anatomical measurements. In his study, Khurshid N et al [6] provided a baseline data pertaining to morphometric details of upper end of tibia in Indian population. As per Gupta C et al [7], there was statistically significant relation between right and left AP diameter of medial condyle, transverse diameter of lateral condyle and area of the lateral condyle as P value was 0.045, 0.001 and 0.046. However, there was no significant relation with other parameters of right and left side as $P > 0.05$.

As per Gandhi S et al [8], on comparing the two condyles, both anteroposterior and transverse measurements were greater in medial condyle of both sides. In his study, Mukhia R et al [9] found that the variation in the morphometry of anteroposterior measurements of intercondylar area, mediolateral length and circumference of upper end of tibia in two sides seems to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). It is also same for the study of Anurag SG et al [10]. As per Murlimanju et al [11] for both length and breadth, the dimensions were statistically lower for the lateral tibial condyle than medial. In their study, Babacan S et al [12] conclude that to accomplish designing the knee prosthesis, basis of differences between medial and lateral condyles to be considered.

Conclusion

The present morphometric study of the upper end of the tibia in the West Bengal population provides valuable insights into the anatomical dimensions of the medial and lateral tibial condyles, particularly their anteroposterior (AP) and transverse (TR) measurements. Our findings are largely consistent with previous studies conducted in diverse populations, though minor variations were noted, likely reflecting regional and ethnic differences. Understanding these morphometric parameters is crucial for orthopedic surgeons, especially in procedures such as total knee arthroplasty, fracture fixation, and the design of prosthetic implants. Accurate knowledge of local anatomical dimensions helps improve surgical outcomes, ensures better implant fit, and reduces postoperative complications. Therefore, the data derived from this study holds significant clinical importance and may serve as a reference for future

anatomical and orthopedic research in the Eastern Indian population.

References

1. Reeti R, Akhtar MJ, Kumar B, Sinha RR, Kumar A. Morphometric study of upper end of tibia and its implications in total knee replacement. *Indian Journal of Clinical Anatomy and Physiology*. 2021;8(3):213-8.
2. Ahmad N, Singh D, Dubey A, Jethani SL. Morphometric analysis of proximal end of the tibia. *National Journal of Clinical Anatomy*. 2019 Apr 1;8(2):82-6.
3. Frelat MA, Mittereocker P. Postnatal ontogeny of tibia and femur form in two human populations: a multivariate morphometric analysis. *American Journal of Human Biology*. 2011 Nov;23(6):796-804.
4. Bhadoria P. Morphometric study of proximal end of tibia and its clinical implications in North Indian population. *Journal of the Anatomical Society of India*. 2017 Aug 1;66:S49.
5. Chaitra D, Pai D, Rathnakar P, Remya K. Morphometric Study of Upper End of Tibia in Dakshina Kannada Population. *Journal of Evolution of Medical and Dental Sciences*. 2020 Apr 13;9(15):1252-6.
6. Khurshid N, Afza R. Morphometric study of upper end of tibia: A study done at SKIMS medical college Srinagar.
7. Gupta C, Kumar J, Kalthur SG. A morphometric study of the proximal end of the tibia in South Indian population with its clinical implications. *Saudi Journal of Sports Medicine*. 2015 May 1;15(2):166-9.
8. Gandhi S, Singla RK, Kullar JS, Suri RK, Mehta V. Morphometric analysis of upper end of tibia. *Journal of clinical and diagnostic research: JCDR*. 2014 Aug;8(8):AC10.
9. Mukhia R, Wahekar K. The upper end of tibia of Nepalese adults: a morphometric study. *Journal of Health and Allied Sciences*. 2020 Oct 16;10(2):78-81.
10. Anurag SG. MORPHOMETRIC STUDY OF THE PROXIMAL END OF TIBIA. *Int J Acad Med Pharm*. 2023;5(3):1736-8.
11. Murlimanju BV, Purushothama C, Srivastava A, Kumar CG, Krishnamurthy A, Blossom V, Prabhu LV, Saralaya VV, Pai MM. Anatomical morphometry of the tibial plateau in South Indian population. *Italian Journal of Anatomy and Embryology*. 2016:258-64.
12. Babacan S, Kafa İM. Morphometric Analysis of Tibial Plateau for Knee Arthroplasty and Prosthesis Design: Morphometric Analysis of Tibial Plateau. *International Journal of Current Medical and Biological Sciences*. 2022 Mar 14;2(1):57-63.